

CIVAL: CLIMAAX in Valcerrina

Deliverable Phase I

Supporting Information 1: Annexes to the Main Report

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Table A: Overview of stakeholders in the CIVAL project. For each stakeholder, their interest and influence towards the project is presented, alongside the adopted corresponding engagement strategy.

Stakeholder	Type of stakeholder	Interest and influence in the CRA	Engagement strategy
Municipalities within the Union of Municipality	Government	High interest, High influence The results of the CRA can directly support the development of their Municipal Civil Protection Plans. They determine whether the CIVAL project will have a long-lasting impact in local decision-making processes associated with the prevention and mitigation of climate risks. They have extensive experienced-based knowledge of the territory, something that the CRA seeks to integrate with scientific knowledge	Active engagement – they will be involved throughout the project and actively engaged to tailor the CRA analysis to the local needs and to gain feedback on the results obtained
Local civil protection teams	Government	High interest, High influence The results of the CRA can directly support their emergency operations through the development of new tools and datasets	Active engagement – they will be involved throughout the project and actively engaged to tailor the CRA analysis to their operational needs
Provincial Authority – Civil Protection Department	Government	Low interest, Medium influence Although they may not influence the achievement of objectives of the CRA at the local (municipal) level, they are important player for the uptake of the project’s results at higher governance level and for the promotion of the CIVAL approach to other communities	Proactive consultation – they will be proactively informed on the key outcomes of the CRA and consulted to assess whether processes initiated by the CIVAL project could be replicated elsewhere and reflected in the provincial approach to climate change adaptation
Regional Authority – Strategic Planning and Green Economy Department	Government	Medium interest, Medium influence The Regional Strategy on Climate Change highlights the need to include civil society and local institutions in the development of measures to adapt to and mitigate climate change. They are therefore interested in bottom-up initiatives such as the CIVAL project and are important players in the promotion of the CIVAL approach to other communities in the region.	Proactive consultation - they will be consulted early in the project to create synergies between the regional strategy on climate change and the CIVAL project and proactively informed on the key outcomes of the CRA.
River Po Basin Authority	Government	Low interest, Low influence The River Po Basin Authority is responsible for the development of the Po River Flooding and Hydrological Risk Plans across the five regions in which the River Po basin fall in. The plan is then acknowledged and adopted in regional plans. As such, the River Po Basin Authority is	Monitor – the activities of the River Po Basin Authority in terms of flood and hydrogeological risks will be monitored to check for potential changes in their interests and for identifying potential synergies with the project.

		deemed to be less interested and influential than the regional authority for the CIVAL project	
Local residents	Civil society	High interest, medium influence They will directly benefit from the improved level of preparedness achieved by the project. They influence the project's goal of increasing awareness on the impact of climate change by being willing to attend public events and training.	Active involvement – they will be kept informed regularly and involved in the project dissemination and awareness activities
Farmers and agrifood entrepreneurs	Industry	High interest, medium influence They will directly benefit from the improved level of preparedness achieved by the project. They have experience-based knowledge of the agricultural sector and can help the project achieve tangible and locally relevant outcomes by sharing information and data on their practices.	Active involvement - they will be kept informed regularly and involved in the CRA for the agricultural sector
Farmers associations (Coldiretti Alessandria)	Industry	Medium interest, Low influence They represent farmers over a large territory, so they are interested in the results of the CRA for the agricultural sector and could help upscale the solutions proposed by the project in the long term	Keep informed - they will be proactively informed on the key outcomes of the CRA
Local environmental associations (e.g., Madre Selva)	Civil society	High interest, Medium influence They have strong connections in the local community and a deep knowledge of the territory. They can play an important role in awareness rising campaigns and public initiatives targeting the local community	Active involvement – they will be kept informed regularly and involved in the project dissemination and awareness activities
Local clergy authority	Civil society	Medium interest, Medium influence They have strong connections in the local community and a deep knowledge of the territory. They can support the project with the involvement of the community.	Active involvement - they will be kept informed regularly and involved in the project dissemination and awareness activities

Table B: List of extreme climate events in Valcerrina

Type of extreme event	Location	Date	Main sectors affected
Flooding	Gabiano	04/2025	agriculture
Heavy rainfall, landslides	Murisengo	05/2024	infrastructure and private properties
Heavy rainfall, landslides	Moncestino, Odalengo, Mombello	03/2024	road infrastructure
Drought	Perosio di Cerrina	08/2017	agriculture
Heavy rainfall, hail	Valcerrina	04/2022	agriculture
Drought	Alessandria	07/2022	agriculture
Wildfire	Valcerrina	06/2017	natural woodlands, arboriculture and agriculture
Flooding, heavy rainfall	Camino	05/2023	road infrastructure
Wildfire	Cerrina	02/2021	natural woodlands
Heavy rainfall, flooding	Cerrina, Mombello, Solonghello	07/2018	Agriculture, road infrastructure, private properties

Figure A: Comparison of flood extents between JRC maps and regional flood maps (PGRA)

Table C: Comparison of global (MapSPAM) and local datasets on cropping pattern.

Crop	MapSPAM (2010)	National Agricultural Census
Wheat	25%	12%
Soya	1%	10%
Maize	3%	6%
Barley	3%	5%

Figure B: Fire danger index as the combination of FWI and burnable area. Lines in black and blue are the boundary of Valcerrina and Alessandria/Asti provinces, respectively.

Figure C: Gantt chart for Phase II and III